

Standard Operating Procedures for Digital Health - Actigraphy Acquisition

Accelerating Medicines Partnership® SCHIZOPHRENIA

An observational study examining clinical trajectories and predictors of outcomes in the clinical high risk population.

Version 2.5, 11 DEC 2023

Procedure	Visit 1	Visit 2	Visit 3	Visit 4	Visit 5	Visit 6	Visit 7	Visit 8	Visit 9	Visit 10	Visit 11	Visit 12	Visit 13	Visit 14	Visit 15	Visit 16	Conversion
Month	-3 to -1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	18	24	-
Consent Form																	
Interview/Questionnaire																	
Cognitive Tasks																	
MRI*																	
EEG*																	
Blood and Saliva Samples*																	
Actigraphy (daily)																	
Digital Data (daily passive sensing, EMA, audio diary)																	
Free Speech Sampling (audio and facial recording)																	
PSYCHS (audio recording)																	

* In-person visit

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Version Modification Log

Version	Date	Summary of Changes
1.0	13 July 2021	N/A
1.1	9 Sept 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Separated the actigraphy SOP from the EMA + Passive Sensing SOP - Added study overview - Streamlined SOP presentation with 2-column format - Added both mail and in-person Axivity device exchange steps - Added raffle draw system for reimbursement - Added 'Actigraphy Instructions' for participants - Finalised Axivity device setting – 8g, 12.5Hz, low power mode - Changed file labelling convention - Included RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET) steps - Moved additional information to appendix - Added hyperlinks to headings
1.2	16 Sept 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Added table of content - Added time-synchronisation step - Replaced reference to AX3 from 'accelerometer' to 'Axivity device' - Axivity device exchange frequency changed from 40 days to monthly - Updated screenshots to reflect changes
1.3	17 Sept 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finalised file labelling convention - Removed recording date participants mount Axivity device - Updated screenshots to reflect changes
1.4	8 Oct 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated outdated hyperlinks
1.5	5 Nov 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Added version modification log and page number - Added face page - Added 'safely remove device' step
1.6	10 Nov 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Removed Perth from PRESCIENT site list - Added Cologne to PRESCIENT site list
1.7	20 Nov 2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Added 'Actigraphy Instructions' print link
1.8	21 Jan 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlighted AX3 Axivity device as the accelerometer to purchase - Non-English sites to translate Actigraphy Instructions to local language - Specific contact persons for PRESCIENT and ProNET network - Renamed Glossary to Appendix - Included Discharge Issue in Appendix
1.9	09 Mar 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Included specific instructions for RPMS - Elaborated on raffle draw
2.0	25 Mar 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raffle draw to occur within PRESCIENT only - Removed Amsterdam from PRESCIENT site list
2.1	19 Apr 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Moved cleaning safety measure step - Changed raffle currency from USD to AUD
2.2	10 Oct 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Added Santiago to PRESCIENT site list - Changed Mediaflux contact person - Added estimated device charge time - Added disclaimer for Subject Code - Added data upload section for ProNET - Updated outdated hyperlinks - Added notes on RPMS and REDCap forms - Updated RPMS graphic - Added link to Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)
2.3	25 Apr 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated reimbursement schedule for PRESCIENT - Updated Mediaflux contact person - Added printing option for and updated reimbursement schedule in Actigraphy Instructions - Added monitoring progress (DPdash) section
2.4	10 Oct 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated SOP Title as per FDA and NIMH's guidance

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Section 4: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Moved and updated DPdash monitoring progress instructions ○ Added file deletion note ○ Added note about data transfer to DPdash processing time - Section 5: Added instructions for participant withdrawal
2.5	11 Dec 2023	- Updated PRESCIENT contact person
		-

Overview

Note: The terms ‘watch’, ‘actigraphy’ and ‘Axivity device’ will be used interchangeably throughout this document.

Actigraphy

- A wearable activity sensor that captures movement on a X, Y, Z axis, light and temperature.
- Data collected will be used to determine sleep, sedentary, and physically active periods (i.e., sleep-wake cycles).

Device

- Data will be collected via an AX3 Axivity device mounted to a waterproof wristband.

Data configuration and format

- The AX3 Axivity device is configured via the OMGUI software and stored in .cwa (raw) format.

Axivity device exchange

- AX3 Axivity devices need to be exchanged monthly for 12 months, due to limited battery and memory space.
- Exchanges will be done either in person or via mail*.
 - *First exchange must be done in person.
- PRESCIENT: Participants will be reimbursed 5 AUD[^] and entered in a 100 AUD[^] raffle for every Axivity device returned**.
 - **Recommendation: One 100 AUD raffle per 10 participants.
 - [^]Please convert from AUD to your local currency for reimbursement.
- Where possible, one research assistant should be assigned to the same participant for the duration of the study.

RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET)

- Each month’s form corresponds to one Axivity device ID^{^^}.
 - ^{^^}The same form will need to be filled in multiple times (e.g., device configuration, device exchange, device return & data upload).
- Protocol deviations and notes must be entered in the month corresponding to the Device ID along with dates.
 - Example: “20221019 - participant took off Axivity device due to work.”

File labelling format[#]

Example: Axivity device #77703 configured on 17th September 2021 for Melbourne participant 12345.

- The OMGUI software will automate all variables of the file name except for the date.
 - [#]See [Appendix](#) (end of document) for notes on each variable.

Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

- Click [here](#) to view frequently asked questions.
 - ^{^^} Copy this if the link above does not work: <https://nih.box.com/s/6ztxi0yl9ujacqgw1b2rp8g56rcqv8u>

1. Study setup

Note: Only needs to be completed once at the beginning of the study.

1.1. Equipment needed

Equipment	Usage
Axivity AX3 device [^]	- Waterproof sensor that needs to be exchanged monthly
Axivity wristband [^]	- Mounts Axivity device on participant's wrist (waterproof silicone)
Micro USB cable [^]	- Charges and transfers Axivity device data
70% isopropyl alcohol	- For cleaning Axivity device in accordance with COVID-19 safety measures
Printed instructions	- Instructions for mounting Axivity device to wristband, watch-wearing, cleaning recommendations, and mailing instructions (see Section 3.2. & link)
Prepaid postal envelope [#]	- For sending Axivity devices to participants** - For participants to return used Axivity devices** **recommendation: use express postage with insurance and tracking
Bubble wrap [#]	- To protect Axivity device during postage** **unless prepaid envelope already has padding (click here for example)
<i>Optional</i>	
Multi-dock charger	- For charging multiple Axivity devices at once** **recommended for sites with many participants (click here for example)
Address label sticker [#]	- For printing participant's address used for labelling postal envelope** **recommended over handwriting addresses to minimise mistakes (click here for example)
Electronic contact cleaner	- For cleaning Axivity device's connector pins if there is a built-up in debris** **recommended only if debris is excessive (click here for example)

[^]Purchasable from [official Axivity website](#)

[#]For Axivity devices exchanged via mail

1.2. Software installation

- To configure the Axivity device, the OMGUI software and drivers are needed.
- System requirements:
 - o Windows PC with XP SP3 or later (**software will not work on Mac or Linux**)
 - o Microsoft .NET Framework v3.5 or later
- Administrator privileges are required to install software.

<p>1. Download the OMGUI software here.</p> <p>Copy this if the link above does not work: https://github.com/digitalinteraction/openmovement/wiki/AX3-GUI</p>	<p>Downloading and Installing</p> <p>The OMGUI software is available from the open source GitHub repository:</p> <p>DOWNLOAD V43 (revisions), Windows, zipped installer.</p>								
<p>2. Unzip the downloaded file and open AX3-GUI-43.exe.</p>	<p>This PC > Downloads > AX3-GUI-43</p> <table border="1"><thead><tr><th>Name</th><th>Date modified</th><th>Type</th><th>Size</th></tr></thead><tbody><tr><td>AX3-GUI-43.exe</td><td>9/07/2021 1:21 PM</td><td>Application</td><td>4,614 KB</td></tr></tbody></table>	Name	Date modified	Type	Size	AX3-GUI-43.exe	9/07/2021 1:21 PM	Application	4,614 KB
Name	Date modified	Type	Size						
AX3-GUI-43.exe	9/07/2021 1:21 PM	Application	4,614 KB						
<p>3. If your device does not have the Microsoft .NET Framework v3.5, you will be prompted to download it.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Click 'OK'. <p>If your device already has Microsoft .NET Framework v3.5, skip to Step 6.</p>	<p>Setup</p> <p>! Your system must have the runtime for Microsoft .NET 3.5 -- download now? ...or manually from: http://tinyurl.com/dotnet35setup</p> <p>Alternatively, you can enable the feature:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Press Windows+R, enter "appwiz.cpl"2. Click 'Turn Windows features on or off'3. Select '.NET Framework 3.5 (includes .NET 2.0 and 3.0)', and 'OK'. <p>If you get error 0x800f081f:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Press Ctrl+Shift+Esc, Alt+F, N2. Type: DISM.EXE /Online /Add-Capability /CapabilityName:NetFx3~~~~3. Click 'Create this task with administrative privileges', and 'OK'. <p>If you get error 0x800f0906, you can change your system update source:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Press Windows+R, type "gpedit.msc"2. Select 'Computer Configuration' / 'Administrative Templates' / 'System' / 'Specify settings for optional component installation and component repair' / 'Enabled' / 'Contact Windows Update directly to download repair content instead of Windows Server Update Services (WSUS)'3. Press Ctrl+Shift+Esc, Alt+F, N4. Type: gpupdate /force5. Click 'Create this task with administrative privileges', and 'OK'. <p>OK Cancel</p>								
<p>4. Press Windows key + R, enter 'appwiz.cpl' in the field and click 'OK'.</p>	<p>Run</p> <p>Type the name of a program, folder, document or Internet resource, and Windows will open it for you.</p> <p>Open: appwiz.cpl</p> <p>OK Cancel Browse...</p>								

5. Click 'Turn Windows features on or off'.
- Tick '.NET Framework 3.5 (includes .NET 2.0 and 3.0)' and click 'OK'.

6. Open the AX3-GUI-43.exe file again and proceed to download the software.
- You can create a shortcut of the OMGUI software on the desktop for convenience.

7. At the end of the software download, tick 'Install AX3 Driver' and click 'Finish'.
- Please make sure you do so, **or the software will not run.**

8. OMGUI will occasionally have firmware updates. Please update firmware whenever prompted to.

1.3. Software overview

- Overview of the OMGUI software.

<p>1. Connect the Axivity device via USB to the computer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For desktop computer users, connect Axivity device directly via USB port behind the CPU. 		
<p>2. Open the OMGUI software.</p>		
<p>3. Enable additional view options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select 'View' and tick all options <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional view options <u>will not</u> be saved. Must be enabled every time software is reopened. 		
<p>4. OMGUI software interface</p>		
<p>Device Browser Pane This section will display all Axivity devices connected to your computer</p>		<p>Device Properties Pane This section displays device properties associated with the Axivity device</p>
<p>Data preview window</p>		
<p>Default workspace</p>		
<p>This section will display data that has been downloaded into your Workspace</p>		
<p>Log changes made in software</p>		<p>File Properties Pane This section displays file properties associated with the downloaded .cwa file</p>

1.4. Configuring default software settings

<p>1. Change the default filename:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select Tools > Options 																
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Change the default filename to: {StudyCode}{SubjectCode}_{DeviceId} - Select 'OK'. <p>Note: Copy and paste the default filename directly into the Filename field. These changes will be maintained after closing the software.</p>																
<p>2. Set up Workspace:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click the three dots [...] on the right to change the Workspace's default location. 																
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select Desktop > Make New Folder - Name the folder 'Actigraphy Data' and select 'OK'. 																
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The correct Workspace path should be displayed in OMGUI. 																
<p>3. Configure default Axivity device settings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select device and click 'Record'. 	<table border="1" data-bbox="679 1709 1286 1816"> <thead> <tr> <th>Device</th> <th>Session Id</th> <th>Battery</th> <th>Download</th> <th>Recording</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Default</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>77703</td> <td>0</td> <td>100%</td> <td></td> <td>Stopped</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Device	Session Id	Battery	Download	Recording	Default					77703	0	100%		Stopped
Device	Session Id	Battery	Download	Recording												
Default																
77703	0	100%		Stopped												

a) Input the follow settings into the software:

- Sampling:
 - o Freq. (Hz) – **12.5**
 - o Range ($\pm g$) – **8**
- Recording Time – **Immediately on Disconnect**
- Study:
 - o Study Centre – **Site, Country**
 - o Study Code – **Site ID**
 - o Study Investigator – **Site investigator's name**
 - o Exercise Type – **Research**
 - o Operator – **RA's name**
- Flash during recording – **Disabled**
- Lower Power (Noisier) – **Enabled**
- Unpacked data – **Disabled**

b) Click 'OK'.

Important:

- These settings will only need to be entered once for every computer used to configure Axivity devices.
- Please double check that the sampling frequency (12.5Hz) and range (8g) are configured correctly, and 'lower power (noisier)' is **enabled**.

c) The default settings will be saved in your Workspace in a 'recordSetup.xml' file.

d) **Do not** delete the file.

Name	Date modified	Type
settings	27/08/2021 11:46 PM	File folder
recordSetup.xml	17/09/2021 4:03 PM	XML Document

1.5. Synchronising computer time with the Internet

<p>1. Open date and time settings:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Right click the date and time on the computer's taskbar	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Select 'Adjust date/time'	
<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Tick 'Set the time automatically'- Tick 'Set the time zone manually'- Select 'Sync now'	

2. Preparation for orientation session with participants

- Participant handedness and mailing address should be obtained at screeners, before baseline.

<p>1. Connect the Axivity device via USB to the computer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For desktop computer users, connect Axivity device directly via USB port behind the CPU. 	
<p>2. Open the OMGUI software.</p>	
<p>3. Enable additional view options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select 'View' and tick all options <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional view options <u>will not</u> be saved. Must be enabled every time software is reopened. 	
<p>4. Fully charge Axivity device to 100%.</p> <p>Note: Axivity device can take up to 2 hours to charge from 0%.</p>	
<p>5. Erase data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing data on the device must be removed before configuration. - Select the device, click 'Clear' and 'OK'. <p>Note: If there is no data to erase, the 'Clear' button will be greyed out.</p>	
<p>6. Set up Axivity device for recording:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select device and click 'Record'. 	

a) Input the follow settings into the software:

- Recording Session ID – leave blank
- Subject:
 - o Code – **Participant ID (AMPSCZ ID number)**
(e.g., 123456)
 - o Sex – **To be filled**
 - o Handedness – **To be filled**
 - o Site – **Non-dominant hand**
 - o Notes – **Participant initials (first name, last name)**
(e.g., MJ = Michael Jackson)

b) Click OK.

Important:

- The Recording Session ID *should be left blank*.
- **Reminder:** Participant ID = Only numerical part of AMPSCZ ID. Site ID already included in ‘Study Code’.
- If needed, please refer to Section 1.4.3.a. for default Axivity device settings.

- Watch is successfully configured when ‘Always’ is displayed.

- Safely remove device from computer.

7. Cleaning (in accordance with COVID-19 safety measures):

- Disinfect Axivity devices and wristbands by wiping the surfaces using 70% isopropyl alcohol.

Important:

- Please avoid soaking the Axivity device’s connector pins with alcohol and only wipe the plastic surface.

8. Update actigraphy run sheet on:

RPMS (PRESCIENT)

- Please fill in the fields below:

REDCap (ProNET)

- Fill in ‘Digital Biomarkers Axivity Onboarding’ alongside the steps above.

Orientation (Baseline - Month 0)

Assessment Date: 19/08/2022

ACTIGRAPHY PARTICIPANT LOG

1. Date device exchanged (i.e., in-person): 17/08/2022

2. RA in charge: John Doe

Session and Device Information

3. Device configured: 1. Yes

4. Axivity device ID: 71111 (5-digit)

5. Device configuration year: 2022 (4-digit)

6. Device configuration month: 08 (2-digit)

7. Device configuration day: 16 (2-digit)

8. Device file name: ME00011_71111_20220816.cwa

9. Configured device disinfected: Select

10. Device fully charged: Select

11. Device given to participant: Select

12. Device returned to RA: Select

13. Returned device disinfected: Select

14. Configuration date added to end of file name: Select

15. Axivity device data uploaded to Mediaflux server: Select

16. The data is presented on DPdash: Select

Note: 'Device file name' will auto-populate when you select 'Update'.

3. Orientation session with participants (in person)

3.1. Pre-orientation

1. Familiarise yourself with the Actigraphy Instructions below (see Section 3.2.)	
2. Watch this video (0:00 - 0:50) for a demonstration of how the wristband and Axivity device should be mounted. Important: - Please <u>do not</u> follow the instructions after 0:50, they are incorrect and not relevant to our study. - Copy this if the link above does not work: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R8kqGg2pcwE	
PRESCIENT	ProNET
3. Email or print the Actigraphy Instructions from here for participants to take home. Important: - Copy this if the link above does not work: https://nih.box.com/s/89yic8ezby3x5hmv6k9ynjajwwojqvp5 - For non-English sites, please translate the Actigraphy Instructions to your local language if you have non-English speaking participants.	3. Email or print the Actigraphy Instructions from here for participants to take home. Important: - Copy this if the link above does not work: https://nih.box.com/s/0sucofpajmq57s4ntna07pnqikl3vi7 - For non-English sites, please translate the Actigraphy Instructions to your local language if you have non-English speaking participants.

3.2. During orientation

- Go through the instructions below with the participant.

Actigraphy Instructions

- For this component, you will be wearing an actigraphy watch (like the Fitbit/Apple Watch) for the next 12 months.
 - o It will measure your sleep-wake cycle and physical activity levels.
- **Do not take off the watch** at anytime and carry on with your day-to-day activity like usual.
- The watch is waterproof and can be worn when showering and bathing, but must **not be worn** when diving, swimming, or when using sauna/steam rooms.
- Wear the watch on your non-dominant hand.
- Mount the Axivity device to the wristband like this:

<p>1.</p> <p>Locate the arrow on the AX3 and align this with the small arrow on the underside of the band.</p>					
--	---	--	---	--	---

- The watch engraving should always be facing the left side of the wrist (regardless of which hand the watch is worn on):

- If you must remove the watch for any reason (e.g., work, swimming, diving, sauna/steam rooms, health purposes), please:
 - o Let me know.
 - o Put it on immediately once you're able to do so.
- If you experience any irritation or allergic reaction from the wristbands, please let me know immediately.
- If you would like to clean the wristband, you can do so with a gentle handwash.
- The Axivity device needs to be **exchanged monthly** due to its limited battery and memory space.
- PRESCIENT: You will be reimbursed 5 AUD and entered in a 100 AUD raffle for every Axivity device returned.

For mail exchanges:

- Postage will be paid for by the research team.
- **Important:** When you receive a new Axivity device via mail, please:
 - o Put it on immediately.
 - o Put the old Axivity device in the paid return envelope and **mail it back to me as soon as possible**, as we only have a limited number of Axivity devices.

* For non-English sites, please translate the Actigraphy Instructions to your local language if you have non-English speaking participants.

- Watch [this video \(0:00 - 0:50\)](#) together with your participant and stop at 0:50.
- Ensure that the participant has mounted the Axivity device and wristband correctly.
- Email or give a physical copy of the Actigraphy Instructions for the participant to take home*.
- For mail exchanges, double check with the participant that their mailing address is updated on RPMS/REDCap. If not, note the correct address down and update RPMS/REDCap accordingly.

- Update actigraphy run sheet and record any device exchange issues and protocol deviations on:

<p>RPMS (PRESCIENT)</p> <p>- Please fill in the fields below:</p>	<p>REDCap (ProNET)</p> <p>- Fill in Digital Biomarkers Axivity Onboarding alongside the steps above.</p>
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Orientation (Baseline - Month 0)

Assessment Date: 19/08/2022

ACTIGRAPHY PARTICIPANT LOG

1. Date device exchanged (i.e., in-person): 17/08/2022

2. RA in charge: John Doe

9. Configured device disinfected: Select

10. Device fully charged: Select

11. Device given to participant: Select

12. Device returned to RA: Select

13. Returned device disinfected: Select

14. Configuration date added to end of file name: Select

15. Axiivity device data uploaded to Mediaflux server: Select

16. The data is presented on DPdash: Select

17. Have you familiarised yourself with the Actigraphy Instructions? Select

18. Have you watched [this video](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R8kqGg2pcwE) (0:00 - 0:50) for a demonstration of how the wristband and Axiivity device should be mounted? Copy this if the link above does not work: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R8kqGg2pcwE> Select

19. Have you printed the actigraphy instructions for the participant? Select

20. Have you gone through the actigraphy instructions with the participant? Select

21. Have you watched the mounting demonstration video with the participant? Select

22. Has the participant mounted the Axiivity device correctly? Select

23. Has the participant worn the wristband correctly? Select

24. Has the participant received a copy of the actigraphy instructions? Select

25. Is the participant's address updated on RPMS (or stored in another safe location)? (for mail exchanges only) Select
If not, update it on RPMS or ensure it is recorded safely elsewhere

26. Record any device exchange issues or protocol deviations:

Note: 'Date device exchanged' = Date device was either mailed out or handed in-person to the participant.

4. Axivity check-in (mail or in-person)

- A new Axivity device needs to be exchanged **a month** from the previous device exchange date to minimize data loss. We recommend exchanges to occur around the time of monthly visits, whether in person or remote.

4.1. Configure new Axivity device for exchange

<p>1. Connect the Axivity device via USB to the computer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For desktop computer users, connect Axivity device directly via USB port behind the CPU. 	
<p>2. Open the OMGUI software.</p>	
<p>3. Enable additional view options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select 'View' and tick all options <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional view options <u>will not</u> be saved. Must be enabled every time software is reopened. 	
<p>4. Fully charge Axivity device to 100%.</p> <p>Note: Axivity device can take up to 2 hours to charge from 0%.</p>	
<p>5. Erase data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing data on the device must be removed before configuration. - Select the device, click 'Clear' and 'OK'. <p>Note: If there is no data to erase, the 'Clear' button will be greyed out.</p>	
<p>6. Set up Axivity device for recording:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select device and click 'Record'. 	

c) Input the follow settings into the software:

- Recording Session ID – leave blank
- Subject:
 - o Code – **ParticipantID (AMPSCZ ID number)**
(e.g., 123456)
 - o Sex – **To be filled**
 - o Handedness – **To be filled**
 - o Site – **Non-dominant hand**
 - o Notes – **Participant initials (first name, last name)**
(e.g., MJ = Michael Jackson)

d) Click OK.

Important:

- The Recording Session ID *should be left blank*.
- **Reminder:** Participant ID = Only numerical part of AMPSCZ ID. Site ID already included in ‘Study Code’.
- If needed, please refer to Section 1.4.3.a. for default Axivity device settings.

- Watch is successfully configured when ‘Always’ is displayed.

- Safely remove device from computer.

7. Cleaning (in accordance with COVID-19 safety measures):

- Disinfect Axivity device by wiping the surface using 70% isopropyl alcohol.

Important:

- Please avoid soaking the Axivity device’s connector pins with alcohol and only wipe the plastic surface.

4.2. Exchanging new Axivity device

<p style="text-align: center;">Mail exchange*</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Prepare Axivity device for mailing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affix address label sticker to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Envelope being mailed out (participant’s address) Envelope participant will use for mail back (research institution’s address) Insert paid return envelope and Axivity device into envelope. <p>Important</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please ensure that the Axivity device is protected with bubble wrap unless the envelope already has padding. 	<p style="text-align: center;">In-person exchange</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Set up meeting with participant and retrieve the old Axivity device from them.
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Mail the Axivity device to the participant. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Give new Axivity device to the participant.
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Check-in with participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “A new Axivity device has been mailed out” “Please mail back the old Axivity device immediately” “Have you kept the watch on at all times?” “Are you having any difficulties mounting the Axivity device or wristband correctly?” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If yes, send this video (0:00 – 0:50) to them and ask them to stop watching at 0:50. “Did you experience any other issues?” <p>Important</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please follow up on participants if they do not mail the Axivity device back. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Check in with participants: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Have you kept the watch on at all times?” “Are you having any difficulties mounting the Axivity device or wristband correctly?” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> If yes, watch this video (0:00 – 0:50) with them and stop at 0:50. “Did you experience any other issues?”
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Update actigraphy run sheet and record any device exchange issues and protocol deviations on: 	
<p style="text-align: center;">RPMS (PRESCIENT)</p> <p>- Please fill in the fields below:</p> <p>The screenshot shows a form with the following fields:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment Date: 19/09/2022 ACTIGRAPHY PARTICIPANT LOG 1. Date device exchanged (i.e., mailed / in-person): 19/09/2022 2. RA in charge: John Doe Session and Device Information 3. Device configured: 1. Yes 4. Axivity device ID: 70000 (5-digit limit) 5. Device configuration year: 2022 (4-digit limit) 6. Device configuration month: 09 (2-digit limit) 7. Device configuration day: 16 (2-digit limit) 8. Device file name: ME0001_70000_20220916.cwa 9. Configured device disinfected: 1. Yes 10. Device fully charged: 1. Yes 11. Device mailed / given to participant: 1. Yes 12. Device returned to RA: 1. Yes 13. Returned device disinfected: 1. Yes 14. Configuration date added to end of file name: 1. Yes 15. Axivity device data uploaded to Mediaflux server: 1. Yes 16. The data is presented on DPdash: 1. Yes 17. Record any device exchange issues or protocol deviations: N/A 	<p style="text-align: center;">REDCap (ProNET)</p> <p>- Fill in ‘Digital Biomarkers Axivity Onboarding’ and ‘Digital Biomarkers Axivity Check-in’ alongside the steps above.</p>

*Note that extreme temperatures (cold or heat) reduce the capacity of the battery (including sudden failure) and could interfere with data collection when mailing Axivity devices. Use judgment regarding participant and environmental conditions when deciding whether to use mail or in-person exchange.

4.3. Disinfect old Axivity device

1. After receiving the Axivity device from participants, clean them in accordance with COVID-19 safety measures:
 - Disinfect Axivity device by wiping the surfaces using 70% isopropyl alcohol.
 - If there is a build-up of debris near on the connector pins, please clean it carefully using a soft brush and use electronic contact cleaners if necessary.

Important:

- Please avoid soaking the Axivity device's electric component with alcohol and only wipe the plastic surface.

4.4. Downloading Axivity device data

<p>1. Connect the Axivity device via USB to the computer.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For desktop computer users, connect Axivity device directly via USB port behind the CPU. 	
<p>2. Open the OMGUI software.</p>	
<p>3. Enable additional view options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select 'View' and tick all options <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional view options <u>will not</u> be saved. Must be enabled every time software is reopened. 	
<p>4. Download raw (.cwa) Axivity device data on OMGUI software:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select the device and click the 'Stop' button to stop data recording. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click the 'Download' button to download the watch data. <p><i>Depending on the file size, this might take some time.</i></p>	
<p>5. Watch data will be saved to your Workspace:</p> <p>Path - C:\Users\'username'\Desktop\Actigraphy Data\</p>	
<p>6. Add date to file name:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Select the downloaded data file and note the 'Time Start' date in the File Properties Pane (bottom right). <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time Start = Date Axivity device was configured. - Date format in OMGUI = YYYY-MM-DD 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click the	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add the date^ (<i>that was noted earlier</i>) to the filename. <p>^Date format [YYYYMMDD]</p> <p>Important:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To edit files in Workspace, OMGUI must be closed. 	
<p>7. Double check that the filename matches the participant's details in RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET).</p>	

4.5. Uploading data to Mediaflux server (PRESCIENT)

<p>1. Contact Sophie Tod (sophie.tod@orygen.org.au) to request for a new user account. Provide your site, name, role, and email address.</p>	
<p>2. After receiving your login details, go to Mediaflux Desktop (unimelb.edu.au) and enter in the domain, username and password provided.</p> <p>Note: See Appendix for additional notes on Mediaflux.</p>	
<p>3. Double click on 'Asset Finder' on the left-hand side column.</p>	
<p>4. Click on Projects > PRESCIENT > your site ID (e.g., 'PrescientME' for Melbourne).</p> <p>Note: Your folders may look slightly different from the screenshots depending on your access level.</p>	
<p>5. Select the 'Actigraphy' folder.</p>	
<p>6. a) If you have not uploaded data for this participant before, create a new folder.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Right-click the 'actigraphy' folder Select 'Create Sub-Collection' Name the folder the Participant ID. Leave 'description' & 'model' blank. Select the newly created participant folder to upload files 	
<p>b) If you have already uploaded data to this folder for this participant, select the participant's folder.</p> <p>Important: - Double-check ID against participant's record in RPMS to ensure you are selecting/creating the correct folder.</p>	
<p>7. Open 'Actigraphy Data' and drag the .cwa file to the relevant Mediaflux folder. This will copy the file into the folder.</p>	

8. A dialog box will pop up asking you to Choose Importer.

- Select Generic > Proceed

9. A second dialog box will pop up. Keep settings as they are and select 'Import Files'.

10. The uploaded file will be visible in the middle panel when you click on the relevant folder.

Note: Actigraphy data may take 1-2 days before accurately appearing on DPdash.

11. Update actigraphy run sheet on RPMS (PRESCIENT) by filling in the fields below:

9. Configured device disinfected:	Select
10. Device fully charged:	Select
11. Device given to participant:	Select
12. Device returned to RA:	Select
13. Returned device disinfected:	Select
14. Configuration date added to end of file name:	Select
15. Activity device data uploaded to Mediaflux server:	Select
16. The data is presented on DPdash:	Select

12. Only delete actigraphy data files from the computer after:

- Three months (or follow your local site's policy)
- Verifying that it has appeared on DPdash

4.6. Uploading data to Yale Secure Box server (ProNET)

<p>1. Access Yale Secure Box:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click 'Continue'. <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Copy this if the link above does not work: https://yalesecure.app.box.com/ - See ProNET Data Transfer SOP for more details. 	<p>Part of Yale Secure Box?</p> <p>Yale Secure Box uses your network credentials to log in to Box. Continue to log in to Box through your network.</p> <p>If you are not part of Yale Secure Box, continue to log in with your Box.com account.</p> <p>Continue (highlighted)</p> <p>Not part of Yale Secure Box</p>
<p>2. Enter your Yale NetID and Password.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Click 'Sign In'. 	<p>Central Authentication Service</p> <p>Manage NetID Account Help</p> <p>Make sure your session is secure</p> <p>Before entering your NetID and password, verify that the URL for this page begins with:</p> <p>https://secure.its.yale.edu</p> <p>To protect your privacy, quit your web browser when you are finished with your session</p> <p>Sign In</p> <p>NetID <input type="text"/></p> <p>Password <input type="password"/></p> <p>Forgot My Password</p> <p>SIGN IN (highlighted)</p> <p>Yale Copyright © 2022 Yale University. All Rights Reserved. Accessibility at Yale Privacy Policy</p>
<p>3. Click on the folder ProNET.</p> <p>Note: Copy this if the link above does not work: https://yalesecure.box.com/s/bzij4f3mmna1oc0uw6bbbm7803r2b8kr</p>	<p>box</p> <p>All Files</p> <p>Recents</p> <p>Synced</p> <p>Notes</p> <p>Trash</p> <p>Search Files and Folders</p> <p>All Files</p> <p>Name</p> <p>ProNET (highlighted)</p> <p>My Box Notes</p>
<p>4. Click on your site-specific folder. For example, for the UCLA site, the folder would be 'PronetLA'.</p>	<p>Yale</p> <p>Search Files and Folders</p> <p>All Files</p> <p>Recent Files</p> <p>Test.boxnote ... Testing123.boxnote ...</p> <p>Name Updated Size</p> <p>PronetLA (highlighted) Today by Philip Wolff 0 Files</p>
<p>5. Select the actigraphy folder (e.g., PronetLA_Actigraphy) and upload the actigraphy data file to the appropriate participant folder.</p> <p>Note: Actigraphy data may take 1-2 days before accurately appearing on DPdash.</p>	<pre> ProNET ├── PronetLA │ ├── PronetLA_Actigraphy │ │ ├── LA11488 │ │ ├── LA12256 │ │ └── LA12345 </pre>
<p>6. Only delete actigraphy data files from the computer after:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Three months (or follow your local site's policy) - Verifying that it has appeared on DPdash 	

4.7. Digital Phenotyping Dashboard (DPdash)

- DPdash is designed to manage and visualise multiple data streams over an extended period of time.
- If there are any issues with DPdash (e.g., unable to view participant data), please contact either Habib Rahimi Eichi (hrahimieichi@mgb.org) from DPACC/PREDICT.

<p>1. Login to DPdash.</p> <p>Notes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Copy this if the link above does not work: https://predict.bwh.harvard.edu/dpdash/ - DPdash is best viewed on Google Chrome. - If you do not have access to DPdash, please contact your Site Investigator so they can add you to the NDA Data User Certification (DUC). 	<p>Welcome to DPdash! Please log in to continue.</p> <p>Username *</p> <p>Password * <input type="password"/></p> <p>Forgot your password?</p> <p><input type="button" value="LOG IN"/></p> <p>Don't have an account? Sign up</p>																																								
<p>2. Overview of DPdash</p>	<p>Search bar</p> <p>Date participant data was last synced with server</p> <p>To easily locate participants, ★(star) those assigned to you</p> <p>Charts Downloadable summary data for monitoring progress</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>PARTICIPANT</th> <th>STUDY</th> <th>LAST SYNCED</th> <th>COMPLETE</th> <th>STAR</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>ME00000</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Today</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>★</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ME00001</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Today</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>★</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ME00002</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Yesterday</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>☆</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ME00003</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Yesterday</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>☆</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ME00004</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Yesterday</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>☆</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ME00005</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Yesterday</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>☆</td> </tr> <tr> <td>ME00006</td> <td>ME</td> <td>Yesterday</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td>☆</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	PARTICIPANT	STUDY	LAST SYNCED	COMPLETE	STAR	ME00000	ME	Today	<input type="checkbox"/>	★	ME00001	ME	Today	<input type="checkbox"/>	★	ME00002	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆	ME00003	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆	ME00004	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆	ME00005	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆	ME00006	ME	Yesterday	<input type="checkbox"/>	☆
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<p>5. Select the Configuration (config.) of interest from the drop-down list:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - combined-digital_biomarker (Yearly) - Digital Biomarker: Axivity Forms and QC (Monthly) - Digital Biomarker: Axivity+Mindlamp (Daily) <p>Note: Actigraphy data may take 1-2 days before accurately appearing on DPdash.</p>	<p>ME00000 - ME Configuration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Combined - Forms - Month 2 Combined - Digital Biomarkers Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp QC Digital Biomarker: Axivity+Mindlamp Digital Biomarker: Axivity+Mindlamp (Daily) combined-digital_biomarker (Yearly) Digital Biomarker: Activity Forms and QC (Monthly) default Combined - Baseline+Month 2 - Dataflow Digital Biomarker: Mindlamp Forms and QC (Monthly) 																																								

a. **Yearly:**
combined-digital_biomarker

- Section relevant for checking actigraphy data quality are outlined in red

Participant	ME00000
Days in Study	407
Days since Mindlamp Onboarding	350
Mindlamp Version (1, 2, or 3)	1
Phone Accelerometer: All Available (>=6h) Days (#)	328
Percentage Availability (%)	94
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	19
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	4
Phone Screen: All Available (>=1h) Days (#)	336
Percentage Availability (%)	96
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	14
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	3
Phone GPS: All Available (>=6h) Days (#)	317
Percentage Availability (%)	91
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	18
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	3
Phone EMA: All Available (complete) Days (#)	217
Percentage Availability (%)	62
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	3
Days since Axivity Onboarding	349
Activity: All Available (>=20h) Days (#)	273
Percentage Availability (%)	85
Data Quality (Avg hours per day) (hr)	23
Availability (1= <25% to 4= >75%)	4
Data Quality (1= <6h/day to 4= >18h/day)	4

b. **Monthly:**
Digital Biomarker: Axivity Forms and QC

- Main config. to use when conducting follow-up:
 - o Red box: Cells coloured orange and below = < 60% threshold

c. **Daily:**
Digital Biomarker: Axivity+Mindlamp

- Daily view not essential for follow-up but helpful for investigating specific issues (e.g., checking if participants have taken watch off)

6. Utilising address bar

- Quickly switch between participants by editing the address bar
- Only include site ID to view all participants from one site

7. DPdash contact person:

- If there are any issues with DPdash (e.g., unable to view participant data), please contact Habib Rahimi Eichi at hrahimieichi@partners.org (DPACC/PREDICT).

5. End of study participation

5.1. Premature ending (withdrawal)

Mail	In-person
1. Send final paid return envelope to participants so they may return <u>both</u> the wristband and Axivity device .	Set up meeting with participants and retrieve <u>both</u> the wristband and Axivity device from them.
2. Thank them for their participation.	
3. Do a final check to ensure that all data is uploaded and labelled correctly.	
4. Update actigraphy run sheet on RPMS (PRESCIENT) / REDCap (ProNET):	
<p>a. If they are opting out from <u>actigraphy only</u> (still enrolled in EMA)</p> <p>In the upcoming check-in form and all subsequent forms:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">Note the reason and date of withdrawal in the 'RA comments' field: (PRESCIENT) Complete the MissingData form as per Section 13.2 of the Data Upload SOP (Section 13.2)	

5.2. Regular ending (final watch exchange)

Mail	In-person								
1. Send final paid return envelope to participants so they may return <u>both</u> the wristband and Axivity device .	Set up meeting with participants and retrieve <u>both</u> the wristband and Axivity device from them.								
2. PRESCIENT: Let participants know that they will be contacted if they win the draw for the raffle.									
3. Thank them for their participation.									
4. Do a final check to ensure that all data is uploaded and labelled correctly.									
5. Update actigraphy run sheet and record any device exchange issues and protocol deviations on:									
RPMS (PRESCIENT)	REDCap (ProNET)								
- Please fill in the fields below:	- Fill in 'Digital Biomarkers Axivity End of 12-Month Study Period' alongside the steps above.								
<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> <p>End of 12-Month Study Period (Month 12)</p> <hr/> <p>END OF 12-MONTH STUDY PERIOD CHECK</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">16. Returned device and wristband disinfected:</td> <td style="padding: 2px;">1. Yes <input type="button" value="v"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">17. Has the participant been informed that they will be contacted if they win the raffle?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;">1. Yes <input type="button" value="v"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">18. Are all Axivity device data uploaded to the Mediaflux server?</td> <td style="padding: 2px;">1. Yes <input type="button" value="v"/></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="padding: 2px;">19. Record any device exchange issues or protocol deviations:</td> <td style="padding: 2px;">N/A</td> </tr> </table> </div>	16. Returned device and wristband disinfected:	1. Yes <input type="button" value="v"/>	17. Has the participant been informed that they will be contacted if they win the raffle?	1. Yes <input type="button" value="v"/>	18. Are all Axivity device data uploaded to the Mediaflux server?	1. Yes <input type="button" value="v"/>	19. Record any device exchange issues or protocol deviations:	N/A	
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6. Financial Reimbursement Schedule (PRESCIENT)

6.1. Monthly financial reimbursement

- Participants will be reimbursed 5 AUD for every Axivity device returned.
- Reimbursement should be processed monthly during check-ins.

6.2. Raffle draw

- A 100 AUD raffle draw will be conducted for every 10 participants who complete the full 12 months of this part of the study. This is to minimise the wait time for participants who have completed the study.
- When 10 participants have completed their 12-month study period, extract the number of Axivity devices returned per participant from RPMS (PRESCIENT).
- Use a random number generator to determine the winners of the raffle draw.

***Important**

- Non-Australian sites, please convert to your local currency.

Appendix

Device ID	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Each Axivity device has a 5-digit unique device ID displayed above the barcode. This is the same unique ID displayed in the Device Browser Pane on OMGUI. 										
Battery life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Duration for full charge = ~90 minutes. 										
Sampling frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Number of samples per second (e.g., 12.5Hz x 60s = 750 datapoints per minute). 										
Sampling range	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The acceleration due to gravity or ~9.81ms⁻². 										
Clock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Axivity device has a built-in real-time clock. 										
Axivity device LED light	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When connected to the computer, the Axivity device has a built-in LED light indicating its status. <table border="1" data-bbox="400 707 1109 949"> <thead> <tr> <th>LED</th> <th>Notes</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>✶ Red rapid flash</td> <td>Battery in precharge, wait up to 60 seconds.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>✶ Red flash</td> <td>Device in bootloader mode.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>● Amber/white pulse</td> <td>Connected to USB power. Allow up to two hours to fully charge (check software for details). Reported battery level is approximate: anything shown over 85% can be considered as a full charge.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>● Solid green/white</td> <td>Connected to power, but not a computer.</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	LED	Notes	✶ Red rapid flash	Battery in precharge, wait up to 60 seconds.	✶ Red flash	Device in bootloader mode.	● Amber/white pulse	Connected to USB power. Allow up to two hours to fully charge (check software for details). Reported battery level is approximate: anything shown over 85% can be considered as a full charge.	● Solid green/white	Connected to power, but not a computer.
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● Solid green/white	Connected to power, but not a computer.										
Troubleshooting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If there are any error messages during watch configuration, please disconnect and retry on a different USB port. <p><u>Discharge Issue</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A discharge error message may pop up if the Axivity device is left uncharged for an extended time (e.g., 3+ months). - If this happens, fully charge and configure the device as per usual, disconnect and reconnect it to the computer, and the error message should disappear. Caution: Device May Have Fully Discharged × <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If any error messages persist, please contact Axivity at info@axivity.com or by clicking here. - Click here for a list of Frequently Asked Questions. 										
Useful links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AX3 user manual (link) - AX3 GUI (link) 										

File label variable:

Variable	Notes					
Site ID	PRESCIENT			ProNET		
	Birmingham, UK	BM	Calgary	CA	Pavia, Italy	PV
	Cologne, Germany	CG	Cambridge UK	CM	Penn	PA
	Copenhagen, Denmark	CP	Georgia	GA	Pitt	PI
	Gwangju, Korea	GW	Hartford	HA	Seoul	SL
	Hong Kong	HK	Harvard/BIDMC	BI	Shanghai	SH
			King's College	KC	Temple	TE

	Jena, Germany	JE	LMU Munich	MU	UC Irvine	IR
	Lausanne, Switzerland	LS	Madrid	MA	UCLA	LA
	Melbourne, Australia	ME	Montreal	MT	UCSD	SD
	Singapore	SG	Mt.Sinai	SI	UCSF/Path	SF
	Santiago, Chile	ST	Northwell	NL	UNC	NC
			Northwestern	NN	WashU	WU
			Oregon	OR	Yale	YA
Participant ID	- Numerical part of AMP SCZ ID					
Device ID	- As displayed above the barcode on the Axivity device and in the Device Browser Pane					
Date	- Date Axivity device was configured, formatted as 'YYYYMMDD'					
File format	- Keep autogenerated file format (.cwa)					

Mediaflux

There are other ways to access Mediaflux - all methods are described here: [link](#)

If you need further assistance with getting started with Mediaflux, please contact Callum Snowball (callum.snowball@orygen.org.au) or request support via University of Melbourne's (UoM) Self-Service Portal (ServiceNow):

- UoM Staff: <http://go.unimelb.edu.au/or96>
- UoM Students: <http://go.unimelb.edu.au/4exr>
- Non-UoM Users: <http://go.unimelb.edu.au/s6qr>